

A Study on the Protections Available under International Instruments and Constitution of India towards Prisoners.

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Abstract

Our nation is known for its democracy and rich culture. The Indian socio-legal mechanism is built on non-violence, liberty, and dignity of the individual. The conviction of a human does not render him non-human and thus they should be treated like one. No one should be deprived of basic human rights available to every person. Prisoner is a human being as well as a natural person or a legal person. If a person gets convicted for a crime, it does not reduce him to the status of a non-person whose rights could be snatched away at the whims of the prison administration. Therefore, imposing any major punishment within the system of prison is conditional upon the absence of procedural safeguards. Therefore, it is mandatory to invoke the rights and constitutional safeguards of the prisoners. Such rights, unless they are propagated and implemented in each corner and the entire perimeter of the prism, are a nullity and betrayal of human faith on the criminal justice delivery system. It is really of concern that a nation like India still lacks a codified specific legislation for the rights of prisoners. However, the role of judiciary in recognising the rights of prisoners through different judgments and interpretations are mention worthy. The increased consciousness regarding prisoners' rights and reform will generate basic human rights for these individuals. Being a convict or being under-trial must not be reason of depriving an individual from his human rights of survival and protections of life. This paper attempts to explain existing constitutional framework in India to safeguard the prisoner's rights and elucidates various judicial pronouncements issued from time to time regarding needs and care of prisoners. It also highlights the existing International Instruments that have immensely contributed to the progressive development of human rights of prisoners.

Key words: Prisoners, Human Rights, Constitutional safeguards, International Instruments.

INTRODUCTION:

In criminal jurisprudence the rights of prisoner are a sensitive topic which is evolving continuously over the time. There are certain rights which are indispensable and vital, for the survival and protection of a human being and are popularly called as human rights and when such enumerated rights are in the Constitution of a country for its citizens, these rights become fundamental rights. Prisoners being human being are also entitled to have these rights but with certain restriction. Constitution of India the progenitor of the renaissance of India has detail provisions of fundamental rights for the citizens of the country. Since India is declared a welfare country in the Preamble it contains several protective measures for the social, economic, and political welfare of the people of the country which are equally accessible to man and woman and prisoners too. However, in the Indian Constitution it is nowhere specifically inscribed any rights to the prisoners but the human rights associated with the dignity of a human being cannot be nullified to the prisoner for being incarceration.

OBJECTIVES: -

The objective of the study is to find out the following few important areas regarding protection and preservation of prisoners.

1. What are the rights available to prisoner during their incarceration. Whether Constitution of India being the fundamental law has implemented these bundles of rights for the protection of the prisoners.
2. Whether judiciary, with judicial pronouncements striving to protect human rights of these prisoners.

PRISONERS RIGHT AND INTERNATIONAL INSTRUMENT

After the world war I and World War II a movement began towards protection of prisoner's right and the coding of the laws of war in the Geneva Convention of 1949. The Geneva Convention III is the first instrument to specifically list protections that must be extended to all prisoners of war and their humanly treatment. International Instrument lays great emphasis towards protection of basic human rights of the prisoners. India too is a signatory to various International Instruments that recognises Prisoner's right and several such instrument contain model rules, principles, and guidelines for treatment of prisoners.

1. Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948:

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights is a declaration adopted by the United Nations General Assembly on 10th December 1948 to which India is also a signatory is the cornerstone of the human rights movement that arose after the barbarous acts that outraged the conscience of mankind after the 2nd world war. It is the clear benchmark for the universal standard of human rights that must be promoted and followed by in all countries. The declaration is a set of principles, very basic for which human are entitled. It contains 30 rights e.g., right to life equality, prohibition against torture and of cruel, inhumane, and degrading treatment or punishment, the prohibition of arbitrary arrest, detention, or exile; the right to a fair trial, the right to be presumed innocent until proved guilty, prohibition of arbitrary arrest etc. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights is not legally binding but it introduces a series of principles to signatory states to adhere to so that they became part of the international community.

2. Standard Minimum rules for treatment of Prisoners:

Standard Minimum Rules is a set of guidelines for the protection of rights of persons who are detained or imprisoned which was first adopted by the united congress on prevention of crime and the treatment of offender at Geneva on 1955, these principles are basically for the prison administration, how to keep various prisoners, their classification, work, food, medical facility etc. These rules are revised and now these standards for treatment of prisoners are known as “Nelson Mandela Rules” which was adopted in 17 December 2015. The revised rules include specific provisions of Solitary Confinement, absolute prohibition, on torture and ill treatment of prisoners.

3. International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights:

International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights is a multi-literal treaty adopted by the United Nations General Assembly on 16th December 1966 and India is a party to this convent. It advocates, the general rule that persons awaiting trial shall be detained in custody, but may be released subject to guarantee to appear for trial. When a person is convicted and subsequently conviction is reversed or pardoned on the ground of miscarriage of justice, the person who has suffered shall be compensated as per Article 14 of the Convent. The Covenant also prescribes that the unconvicted persons should be segregated from convicted person and

should be subject to separate appropriate treatment. The Covenant categorises the undertrials and the convicts. The state parties to the covenant must submit their report to Human Rights Covenant or the measures they have adopted to give effect the rights recognised under the covenant. India being a signatory of International Convention on Civil and Political Rights is legally bound to give effect to the rights of the prisoners recognised under the Covenant.

4. International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights:

This Covenant ensures adequate standard of living of prisoners and guarantees the right to adequate food, clothing, and house, free from hunger, social security, protection of families and children, safe and healthy working conditions and to take part in cultural life.

5. Basic Principles for treatment of Prisoners:

Basic Principles for treatment of Prisoners were adopted and proclaimed by United Nations General Assembly on 14th December 1990. It obligates the state parties to treat the prisoners with respect to their dignity and value as human being. It accredits that prisoners shall retain the human rights and fundamental freedom set out in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. The instrument also provides for abolition of solitary confinement as punishment. This instrument seeks to achieve humanization of criminal justice system as well as the protection of human rights of prisoners.

6. Body of principles for the Protection of all persons under any form of detention or imprisonment.

It was adopted by United Nations General Assembly resolution on 9th December 1988. This principle applies for the protection of all persons under any form of detention or imprisonment. It provides that all persons under any form of detention or imprisonment are to be treated in a human manner and with respect for the inherent dignity of a person. Arrest, detention should be carried out strictly in accordance with the provisions of the law and by competent officials or persons authorised for that purpose. These principles are to be applied to all without distinction of race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national ethnic or social origin, property, birth, or other status. No person under any detention is to be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhumane degrading treatment or punishment.

7. United Nation's Convention against Torture:

It is an international instrument that aims to prevent torture and cruel inhuman, degrading treatment or punishment inflicted the world. India is a signatory to the convention. The convention obliges the state parties to take legislative, administrative, judicial, or other measures in order to prevent torture. Each state parties mandated to ensure that all acts of torture are declared as offences under their criminal law. The convention also says that the victim of torture has right to compensation. Article 17 of the convention also provides for establishment of a committee against torture to carry out the interested functions under the convention. Thus, the convention requires the state parties to ensure protection of prisoners from cruel, inhumane, and degrading treatment inside the prisons.

PRISONER'S RIGHT & INDIAN CONSTITUTION

There are no specific prisoners right mentioned in the Constitution of India. But certain rights which have been enumerated in Part III of the Constitution are available to prisoners too, because a prisoner does not cease to be a human being for being incarcerated. There are certain inalienable, vital rights associated with a human person without which he will degenerate to the level of animal and such essential rights continues with the human being while he is in prison. However, when a convict is placed in a jail, he is deprived of his liberty to move freely throughout the territory or he lost his right to practice a profession. But the Constitution provides them the other freedoms like right to acquire, hold and dispose of property for the existence of which detention cannot be any impediment. Indian Constitution have provisions for the interest of the prisoners, particularly the women while behind the bars. Some of them are:

1. Preamble:

Preamble of the Constitution of India declares it as a social welfare State symbolises the emphasis on justice Social, Economic, Political, Liberty of thoughts, expression, belief faith and worship. The Preamble imposes on the Government under an obligation to act to achieve maximum social welfare which includes protect of undertrials, detunes, convicts in prison.

2. Article 10- Protection as a Citizen:

Article 10 of the Constitution provides that every person who is or is deemed to be a citizen of India shall subject to the provisions if, any law may be made by Parliament continue to be such citizen. Thus, by incarnation a person does not cease to be a citizen. Constitutional rights available to citizen are also available to prisoner although with certain restriction. Rights of citizens can be deprived off only by express enactment of Government made for the purpose and cannot be taken away indirectly.

3. Article 14:

Right against Arbitrary State action and Classification of Prisoner. Article 14 contains the principle of equality. It says that the State shall not deny to any person's equality before the law or the equal protection of the laws within the territory. Article 14 is attracted when any discrimination is alleged against the detainee. In Sunil Batra case Supreme Court held that the operation Article 14 may be passed down for a prisoner but cannot puffed out altogether.

4. Article-19: Freedoms of Prisoners

Article 19 guarantees to the citizens of India six freedoms which are necessary essential to promote certain basic rights of the citizens, and to maintain democratic values of the country. It guarantees some basic, valued natural rights inherent in a person. Among these freedoms, freedoms like 'freedom to move freely throughout the territory of India', 'freedom to reside and to settle', 'freedom to practice any profession or to carry occupation, trade or business' can't be enjoyed by the inmates or convicts because of the very nature of incarceration. But other freedoms like 'freedom of speech and expression', 'freedom to assemble peacefully and without arms' and 'freedom to become member of an association', can be enjoyed by the prisoners. The cardinal goal of imprisonment is correctional, changing the consciousness of the criminal to ensure social protection. The exercise of the freedoms is restricted by the, clauses 2 to 6 of the Article 19 of the Constitution. A legislature cannot restrict these freedoms beyond the requirements of Article 19 (2) to (6). Exercise of these freedoms by the prisoners is also no exception to this general rule.

5. Article 20: Rights against excessive punishment, double jeopardy, and self-incrimination

Article 20 of the Constitution has given the safeguard to the persons accused of crimes. Persons here mean the citizens, non-citizens as well as corporations. Article 20(1) protects a person from receiving a penalty greater than what he might have incurred at the time of his committing the offence. If a prisoner is committed under a warrant for jail custody for specified period but he has been kept more than the specified period, it will be violative of Article 20(1) of the Constitution as it will imply imposition of penalty greater than what he might have incurred.

Article 20(2) provides that no one shall be prosecuted or punished for the same offence more than once. Article 20(3) provides that no person accused of any offence shall be compelled witness against himself. If a person is in prison, he shall not be compelled to discover documents or objects which shall incriminate him. This is an observance of civilized standards in the enforcement of criminal justice system.

6. Article 21: Right to life

Article 21 of the Constitution provides the right to life and personal liberty. This Article provides that 'no person shall be deprived of his life and property except according to procedure established by law'. The Supreme Court of India, by interpreting Article 21 of the Constitution, has developed human rights jurisprudence for the protection of prisoners.

The "Maneka Gandhi" case emphasize is given on the procedures prescribed by law and that must be fair, just and reason. In the cases like Maneka Gandhi, Sunil Batra, Hussainara Khatoon, the Supreme Court has taken the view that the Part III of the Constitution should be given widest possible interpretation. It has been held that right speedy trial, right to have interview with friend, relative and lawyer prisoners in jail from degrading, inhuman, and barbarous treatment, right to abroad, right to live with human dignity, right to livelihood, etc., are fundamental under Article 21 of the Constitution. Thus, the Supreme Court of India has considerably widened the scope of Article 21 and has held that its protection will be available safeguarding the fundamental rights of the prisoners and for effecting prison reforms. The Supreme Court of India has developed Human Rights jurisprudence for the preservation and protection of Prisoner's Right. The concern of the Apex judiciary is evident from the various cardinal judicial decisions.

The decisions of the Supreme Court in Sunil Batra case are a watershed in the development of prison jurisprudence in India. Bhagwati J. has observed in Francis Coralie that right to life

includes the right to live with human dignity and all that goes along with it. In *Olga Tellies*, the Supreme Court emphasized that the term 'life' under Article 21 is not only restricted to the mere animal existence of a person.

More recently in *Mehmood Nayyar Azam v. State of Chhattisgarh*, Supreme Court has observed that it is the sacrosanct duty of the police authorities to remember that a citizen while in custody is not denuded of his fundamental right under Article 21 of the Constitution. In "*Kedre Padhaya V. State of Bihar* several under-trial prisoners were in jail for 8 years without their trial. The court said it as a crying shame on judiciary system which keeps men in jail for years without trial. The court emphasizing on speedy trial as fundamental right of an accused as implicit in Art. 21 Unless due importance is given to the fundamental rights and human rights of the people, the right to life and the right to live with human dignity under Article 21 of the Constitution will have no meaning."

7. Article 22: Arbitrary arrest and detention

Article 22 grants protection to person who is arrested and detained. Detention is of two types, namely punitive and preventive. Punitive detention is to punish a person for an offence committed by him after judicial process. On the other hand, preventive detention means detention of a person without trial and convention the purpose of which is to prevent him from committing an offence soon.

Article 22(1) gives every citizen of India the right to be informed of arrest and the right to consult and be defended by a counsel. Article 22(2) provides every citizen of India the right to be produced before a magistrate within 24 hours, excluding the time required for the journey. It also provides the right to be released after 24 hours unless the magistrate authorizes further detention. However, Article 22(3) says that above safeguards are not available to an alien or a person arrested or detained under a preventive detention law. Article 22 (4) says that the detention of person cannot exceed three months unless an advisory board reports sufficient cause for extended detention. Article 22 (5) says that the ground of detention should be communicated to the detainee and the detainee should be afforded an opportunity to make a representation against the detention order.

Article 22 (6) says that the facts that are against the public interest need not be disclosed. Moreover, Article 22(7) authorizes the Parliament to prescribe the circumstances and the

classes of cases in which a person can be detained for more than three months under a preventive detention law without obtaining the opinion of the advisory board, the maximum period for which a person can be detained in any classes of cases under a preventive detention. Thus, if a person becomes the prisoner in violation of the above Constitutional provisions, it will give rise to Constitutional remedies to the prisoner concerned for the violation of his fundamental rights.

8. Article 23: Rights against exploitation

Article 23 of the Constitution prohibits traffic in human being and beggar and other similar forms of forced labour. In *Peoples Union for Democratic Rights vs. Union of India*, the Supreme Court interpreted the word 'force' very widely and included not only physical or legal force but also force arising from the compulsion of economic circumstances for which person received less than the minimum wages and a person who provides labour or service to another for remuneration which is less than minimum wages, amounts to forced labour under Article 23.

Kerala High Court opined that the prisoners are entitled to payment of reasonable wages for the work taken from them. Article 23(1) is a right guaranteed to a citizen and there is no reason why a prisoner should lose his right to receive wages for his labour. In *State of Gujarat v. Hon'ble High Court of Gujrat* Supreme Court has considered the question: can prisoners be made to do hard labour against their will? Is it hit by Article 23? Should the prisoners who are required to do labour punishment, necessarily be paid wages? The Court ruled that a prisoner sentenced rigorous imprisonment can be made to do hard labour. But, even then he equitable wages for his work it is a social imperative and an ethical compulsion. Extracting somebody's work without giving him anything return is only reminiscent of the period of slavery and the system of beggar. Thus, rigorous imprisonment is not unconstitutional, but no prisoner should be forced to do labour without reasonable wages.

9. Article 25: Right to Religion

Article 25 (1) guarantees to every person the 'freedom of consciousness' and 'the right freely to profess, practice and propagate religion'. Article 25, as its language amplifies, assures to every person subject to public order, health and morality, freedom not only to entertain his religious beliefs, as may be approved of by his judgment and conscience, but also to exhibit his belief in

such outwardly act as he thinks proper and to propagate or disseminate his ideas for the edification of others. Under this provision prisoner can freely profess, practice, and propagate religion. This right is available not only to Indian prisoners but also to foreign prisoners in India, as this Article is applicable not only to citizen but to all.

10. Article 32: Constitutional Remedies

Article 32 confers power on the Supreme Court to enforce fundamental rights. Article 32(1) guarantees the right to move the Supreme Court, by appropriate proceedings, for the enforcement of the fundamental rights enumerated in the Constitution. Article 32(2) which empowers the Supreme Court to issue appropriate orders or directions or writs including writs in the nature of Habeas Corpus, Mandamus, Prohibition, Quo Warranto and Certiorari, whichever may be appropriate, for the enforcement of the fundamental rights. The Supreme Court has entertained several petitions under Article 32 complaining of infraction of fundamental rights of individuals, or of weak or oppressed groups who are unable themselves to take the initiative to vindicate their own rights. The Supreme Court has ruled that under Article 32, it is not necessary that the affected person should personally approach the Court. The Court can itself take cognizance of the matter and proceed *Suo moto* or on a petition of any public spirited individual or body. Ms. Kapila Hingorani (Advocate) filed a writ in the Supreme Court in 1979 based on a series of articles in the Indian Express, exposing the plight of 29,000 Bihar undertrial prisoners. Most of them had served long periods of pre-trial detention. The Court not only proceeded to make the right to speedy trial of the case but passed the order of general release of close to 40,000 under trials who had anguished in jail beyond such maximum period. Many have regarded this case as the first protection of prisoners.

11. Article 39(A): Free Legal Aid to Prisoners

The 42nd Amendment to the Constitution of India has included Free Legal Aid as one of the Directive Principles of the State Policy under Article 39A of the Constitution. The article provides, - "The state shall secure that the operation of the legal system promotes justice, on a basis of equal opportunity, and shall, in particular, provide free legal aid by suitable legislation or schemes or in any other way, to ensure that opportunities for securing justice are not denied to any citizen by reason of economic or other disabilities." Though this Article is not enforceable by Courts, but it obligates the State to take positive action in order to promote the

welfare of the people. "Sheela Barse V. State of Maharashtra" Sheela Barse a journalist wrote to the supreme court of India on custodial violence to women prisoners in police lock up in Bombay. The court provided certain guide lines for providing legal aid and stated that legal assistance to every poor and indigent who is arrested and put in jeopardy of his life or personal liberty is constitutional imperative under Art. 39A, Art. 14, Art. 21 which if not provided will corrode the foundation of democracy and Rule of law. The legal assistance should be provided to an under trial and as well as convict.

12. Article 226: Provision of issue of writs by High Court

Article 226 of the Constitution provides an important mechanism for judicial review. Under this Article, a High Court is empowered to issue directions orders or writs, including writs in the nature of habeas corpus, mandamus, prohibition quo warranto and certiorari for the enforcement of fundamental right and for any other purpose. Prisoner' fundamental rights, except those which have been curtailed by reason of incarnation, cannot be curtailed, or whittled down by legislation. Advantages given under Article 226 cannot be curtailed by any legislation. Even a general public can protect the prisoner's right invoking the provisions of Article 226 under the concept of Public

Interest Litigation. Under the Seventh Schedule of the Constitution of India, the prison administration is to be administered by the respective States. This authority has been entrusted to the State Government by State List, Entry 4. It means Prisons administration will be carried out by the State governments and the same will be responsible for proper governance. The State Government is liable to pay compensation to the prisoners, if awarded, for violation of prisoners' rights.

13. Articles 72 AND 161: Pardon and mercy to prisoners

The Article 72 and 161 of the Constitution contains provision to grant pardon or show mercy to the convicts. Article 72 of the Constitution empowers the President to grant pardons who have tried and convicted of any offence in all cases where the, -

(I) Punishment or sentence is for an offence against a Union Law.

(ii) Punishment or sentence is by a Court Martial. And

(iii) Sentence is a sentence of death.

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The President under Article 72 of the Constitution have the power to grant pardons, reprieves, respites, or remissions of punishment or to suspend, remit or commute the sentence of person convicted of any offence. For example, a death sentence may be commuted to rigorous imprisonment, which in turn may be commuted to a simple imprisonment. The pardoning power of the President is an executive power.

Article 161 of the Constitution gives the Governor power to grant pardons, reprieves, respites or remissions of punishment or to suspend, remit or commute the sentence of any person convicted of any offence against any law relating to a matter to which the executive power of the States extends.

Judicial pronouncement and prisoners right

The Constitution of India has not specially mentioned any right as prisoners' rights but through various judicial interpretations these rights have been recognized. Judiciary plays pivotal role in expanding the fundamental rights enshrined in the constitution to envelope many rights for the detunes to give them protection and justice against the violations.

1. Right of Personal Liberty:

The right of personal liberty has special significance for the prisoners. The term "personal liberty under Art 21 is a compendious term to include within it all those variety of right of a person which go to make up the personal liberty of a man. under Art. 21 convicts are entitled to most precious right that he shall not be deprived of his life and personal liberty, except according to procedure established by law. The "Maneka Gandhi" case has great significance in this context. It opens new vistas in the world of judicial activism in the country. It makes profound and beneficial impact on the administration of criminal justice system. In *Kharak Singh vs State of Uttar Pradesh*, the Supreme Court rules that the term life connotes more than mere existence like that of an animal. The right to life cannot be restricted to a mere animal existence, it connotes something more than just the physical survival of a being.

2. Delay in speedy trial:

In *Hussainara Khatoon's* case, in which under trial prisoner were languishing in jail for years waiting for trial, *Bhagwati j.* held that although unlike the American constitution speedy trial is not specifically mentioned in Indian constitution as fundamental right, it is implicit in the

broad sweep and content of Art. 21 as interpreted in “Maneka Gandhi's” case and ordered the Bihar Government to acquit the under-trial prisoners on their personnel bond. In Hussainara Khatoon No.2 & No.3 the court reinforced the same principle and ordered the concerned session judge to complete the trial expeditiously. In denial of this right the under-trial prisoner can approach the Supreme Court for enforcing their right. Elaborating the scope of Article 21 in the case of "Babu Singh V. State of U.P it was held that refusal to grant bail in a murder case without reasonable ground would amount to deprivation of personal liberty. Rehman Análey V. R S. Nayak the Supreme Court provided a detailed guide line for Speedy trial. The court hold that the right to speedy trial flowing from Art. 21 is available to accused at all stages namely i.e., stage of investigation, inquiry, trial, appeal, revision, and retrial. In Veena Sethi V. Bihar court also held that continued detention is the violation not only of dignity but also their fundamental rights under Art 21 of the constitution.

3. Right against solitary confinement:

This issue first came before Supreme Court in the historic "Sunil Batra v. Delhi Administration” case. The question was whether solitary confinement imposed upon prisoners who were under sentence of death was violative of Article 14, 19, 20, 21 of the constitution.

4. Right of reading and writing:

In state of Maharashtra vs Prabhakar¹ The Article 21 of the Constitution was expanded to include the right of reading and writing books to the prisoner while in jail.

5. Restriction on minimum freedom of movement:

In Prem Shankar Shukla vs Delhi Administration² the court pronounced that Indian constitution recognizes several rights to the convicted prisoner although he/she is not allowed to enjoy all the fundamental rights that have given to a common person, however a prisoner can also enjoy certain fundamental rights as inalienable.

6. Right Against Handcuff:

¹ AIR 1966 SC 424; 1966 (1) SCR 702,

² 930 Sec 1999 Cri LJ, Journal Section 36 at 40)

To handcuff is to hoop and to punish humiliatingly. It is necessarily implicit in Article 14 and 19, that when there is no compulsive need to filter a person links, it is sadistic, capricious, despotic, and demoralizing to humble man and menacing him. The minimum freedom of movement which even a detainee is entitled to under Article 19 cannot be cut down by application of handcuff.

7. Right to have free legal Aid:

Right to have free legal aid is another important right the under-trial prisoners receive under Indian Constitution. Article 39 A of the Constitution of India it is the obligation of the state to provide free legal aid to the under-trial prisoner. It is the prerogative of the state that the poor, deprived prisoner should provide free legal aid and state must pay the lawyer an amount of fees fixed by the court. In *Madhav Hayawadan Rao Hoskot vs State of Maharashtra*³ the Apex Court opined that free legal aid is state's duty but not charity and if the prisoner is unable to exercise his constitutional and statutory right of appeal including special leave to appeal for want of legal assistance, the court will provide legal assistant under Article 29, 39A and Article 142.

In *Sheela Bare vs State of Maharashtra* Supreme Court held that legal aid to the poor indigent accused is a Constitutional mandate. *Khalivi vs State of Bihar*⁴ Supreme Court observed that the obligate of the free legal aid to the poor accused is not only in the trial of case but even for the first when the accused is brought before Magistrate. It is essential for reasonable, fair, and just procedure for a person accused of an offence and is implicit in Article 21 of the constitution.

8. Right of women prisoner to live with their children:

In the case of *R. D. Upadhyaya vs. State of Andhra Pradesh and others*,⁵ the Honourable Supreme Court recognises the Rights of Women Prisoners and Children living with their mothers in jails. While acknowledging some positive steps taken in this regard, the Court noted that "a lot more is required to be done in the States and Union Territories for looking after the interest of the children" And went on to issue holistic development of the Children of women

³ (1978) 3 SCC 544, AIR 1978 SC 1548

⁴ AIR 1981 SC 928 of 930

⁵ AIR 2006 SC 1946

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prisoners and pregnant prisoners. The Child born out of prisoner mothers, their birth place should not be recorded as 'prison' on their birth certificate.

9. Right Against Solitary Confinement:

Now criminologists and many others regard solitary confinement as something extremely cruel and dehumanizing. It means the slow and continuous deterioration of the. The issue first came before Supreme Court in the historic "Sunil Batra v. Delhi Administration" case. The question was whether solitary confinement imposed upon prisoners who were under sentence of death was violative of Article 14, 19, 20, 21 of the constitution.

10. Right against in human treatment and torture:

The Court also bestowed its attention to the question of maltreatment of under-trials and convicted prisoners in prison and police custody. Here the guiding motto of the Court has been imprisonment does not 'ipso facto, desert the fundamental rights of prisoner. The Court condemns police brutality and torture of prisoners and under-trials. In Raghbir Singh V, State of Haryana" the Supreme Court observed –We are deeply disturbed by the diabolical recurrence of police torture resulting in terrible scare in the minds of common citizens that their lives and liberty are under a new peril when the guardians of the law gore human rights to deaths."

In "Ram Murthy V State of Karnataka" discussed on the issue of torture and ill treatment of prisoners and points out ill treatment of prisoner in paras 29 to 34 of the Judgement. the case of "Sunil Batra V Delhi Administration is a glaring example of cruel inhuman treatment of the prisoner. This right finds its place in Article 7 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights but has not been expressly enumerated in Part III of the Indian Constitution. The court converted this letter into a habeas corpus petition and approved and reiterated the specific guidelines in Sunil Batra case No. 1. The court gave the following directions to the Central and State governments and Jail authorities. –

(1) That the petitioner's torture was illegal and shall not be subjected to any such torture until fair procedure is complied with

(2) No corporal punishment or personal violence on the petitioner shall be inflicted

(3) Lawyers nominated by the D. M. Session Judge, High Court and Supreme Court will be given all facilities to interview, right to confidential communication with prisoners, subject to

discipline and security considerations. Lawyers shall make periodical visit and report the concerned Court the result of their visits

(4) Grievance deposit boxes shall be maintained in jail & which shall be opened by D. M. and his sessions Judge frequently. Prisoners shall have access to such boxes.

(5) D.M. and sessions Judge shall inspect jails once every week, shall make enquiries into grievances remedial and take suitable actions

(6) No solitary or punitive cell, no hard labour or charge, denial or privileges and amenities, no transfer to offer prison as punishment shall be imposed without judicial approval of the sessions Judge.

Another landmark judgment came in Francis Carolie Mullin v. Admn. Union Territory of Delhi case in which Supreme Court point out that in Art. 21 it is implicit that the prisoner has right of protection against torture and inhuman and degrading treatment. The custodial death of business tycoon Pillai in Tihar Jail, Nilabati Behra case are worth mentioning.

11. Right Against Delayed Execution:

The right against delayed execution of death Sentence came before the court in T.V. Vatheeswaran Vs. State of Tamil Nadu. In "Sher Singh Vs. State of Punjab" is another case that focuses more light on the question of delay in execution. The court says that the prolonged detention to await the execution of a sentence of death is an unjust, unfair, and unreasonable procedure and the only way to undo the wrong is to quash the death sentence.

Conclusion:

Imprisonment is one of the common modes of punishment available to the courts to deal with the criminal offenders. They are confined with the intention of correction by restricting their personal liberty. However, prisoner does not cease to be a human being after being confined to the four walls of the prison. They are entitled to basic human rights which are sacrosanct despite imprisonment. The minimum rights should be allowed to the prisoners during captivity. The International human Rights instruments has justified the existence of protections available to the offenders. The Indian Judiciary has manifolded the gravity of these legal commitments and

safeguards from time to time with worthy decisions. However, the success of reformation and correction will be only possible with dedication of officers, empathy of system and rights attitude of the offenders.

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